

EDUCATIONAL AND EDUCATIONAL GAMES AS A NEW FORMAT OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The present article considers the role of games in teaching a foreign language. A well planned and methodologically thought out game provides comprehensive acquisition of the material being studied and mastering efficient speaking skill.*

Keywords: *game, game activity, teaching, communication, speech, educational technology.*

УЧЕБНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ИГРЫ КАК НОВЫЙ ФОРМАТ ИГРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается роль игр в обучении иностранному языку. Грамотно спланированная и методически продуманная игра обеспечивает всестороннее усвоение изучаемого материала и овладение грамотной речью.*

Ключевые слова: *игра, игровая деятельность, обучение, общение, речь, образовательная технология.*

Gaming technology is an effective teaching tool that activates the mental activity of students, makes the learning process attractive and interesting, and makes students worry and worry. This is a powerful incentive to increase motivation to master a foreign language. The game always involves making a decision — what to do, what to say, how to win. This circumstance sharpens the mental activity of students. The developing value of the game lies in its very nature, for the game is always emotions, and where emotions are there is activity, attention and imagination are there, and thinking works there. For children of primary and secondary school age, the brightness of perception, ease of entering the images are characteristic, therefore the most effective forms of teaching foreign languages at these stages, in the opinion of the author of this experience, are didactic and role-playing games.

Unlike games in general, a didactic game has an essential feature — the presence of a clearly defined learning goal and the corresponding pedagogical result. The didactic game has a stable structure that includes the following main components:

1. Game Design.
2. Rules.
3. Game action.
4. Cognitive content or didactic tasks.
5. Equipment.
6. Results of the game.

Game design is expressed in the name of the game. It is laid down in the didactic task that needs to be solved in class, and gives the game a cognitive character, imposes certain requirements on its participants with regard to knowledge.

The basis of the didactic game is cognitive content. It consists in the assimilation of the knowledge and skills that are used in solving a learning problem posed by the game. In order to

increase the motivation to master foreign languages, didactic games are used in the classroom to solve the following tasks:

1. To set up students in a working way, introduce them into a foreign language atmosphere. Schoolchildren come to us for a lesson from the “world of the native language,” therefore it is important to create for them an atmosphere of communication, psychological communicative comfort. In this regard, it is advisable to use at the beginning of the lesson not the stereotypical report of the person on duty, but to “invite” your favorite fairy-tale characters, for example, the Scattered Man, who confuses the day and the day of the week, Snow White — the week and the dwarfs — the days of the week.

2. Forming students certain skills. For example: Adman collected portfolio. Guess what he put there!

3. Develop students' specific speech skills. For example: After studying the theme “Apartment”, you can play this game: — Three pigs decided to furnish their house with furniture. Let's help them do it!

4. To teach students to communicate in a foreign language. — Competition for the most polite interlocutor. — Competition for the best compliment.

5. Develop the necessary abilities and psychological functions.

— Are you attentive? Man Scattered gathered on a journey. What extra he took? — “Snowball”.

P1. “I'm going on a trip and put a toothbrush in my suitcase.”

P2. “I'm going on a trip and put a toothbrush and soap in a suitcase ... etc.”

6. Expand students' knowledge of regional geography and language. To do this, use quiz, correspondence travel, preparation for traditional holidays.

7. Expand school vocabulary.

— rhyming;

— accompanying words with facial expressions or gestures;

— flower — seven-color (speech task — the development of the ability to call color, a survey of vocabulary).

8. Relieve tension. After intense mental activity, students should be given a little rest, to cause positive emotions. Types of relaxation can be funny rhymes, songs, games, which are accompanied by movements.

9. Give an adequate assessment of the activities of students. Many teachers oppose the mark, which hurt poorly performing children in pain, discourage their desire to learn. The point is not in the assessment, but in how it is served. It is not necessary to use a figure as an estimate, it can be replaced, for example, with a chip, an asterisk, etc.

10. To form students' ability to assess their capabilities. Judge the feasibility of their activities, freely compare themselves with others, and the child should try most of the solutions in practice. The game gives him the opportunity to the results of their actions, with the successes or failures of other children. Such an assessment — worked out by our own efforts — is much more accurate. It contributes to the further revitalization of the child.

Role-playing includes elements of both dramatization and “simulation”. Therefore, role-playing can be considered as a universal form of organization of communication in the classroom.

Inclusion of games in the learning process provides an opportunity for language practice, offers context and conditions under which the language is fully used as a linguistic phenomenon and means of communication, acts as a diagnostic tool for both teacher and student, highlighting the difficulties encountered, develops creative thinking abilities.

Besides the fact that games have great methodological value, they are just interesting both for the teacher and the student. Knowledge acquired without interest, not tinged with one's own positive attitude, emotions, does not become useful.

Therefore, in games, in order to achieve a better result, it is necessary to combine knowledge of the language, psychology and teaching methods.

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